

Infestation and yield losses caused by rice gall midge on 4 rice varieties at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, Thailand, 1979.

Treatment		Damaged tillers (%)		Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)
Rice variety	Insecticide ^a	30 DT	55 DT	55 DT			
Leaung-Laung	treated	0.9	1.8	7.1	4.5	2.909	–
Leaung-Laung	untreated	2.4	25.0	8.4	3.1	1.951	32.9
RD1	treated	1.4	1.0	11.4	5.5	2.323	–
RD1	untreated	3.5	21.5	12.0	4.4	1.866	19.7
Dok-Ma-Li 105	treated	0.6	0.4	10.1	5.7	2.033	–
Dok-Ma-Li 105	untreated	0.9	19.2	10.7	4.9	1.828	10.1
Niew-San-Pa-Tong	treated	1.3	2.2	7.9	4.6	2.740	–
Niew-San-Pa-Tong	untreated	2.3	26.5	9.7	4.4	2.522	7.9

^aFor gall midge control, carbofuran 3% G was applied to treated plots at the rate of 1 kg a.i./ha 2 times – 20 and 40 days after transplanting (DT).

divided into 4 equal subplots where the 4 rice varieties were transplanted at 3 seedlings/hill. Each replication consisted of 2 main plots, treated and untreated. The treated plots received carbofuran 3% G at 1 kg a.i./ha 2 times, 20 and 40 days after transplanting (DT).

The percentages of damaged tillers caused by the rice gall midge among the

4 untreated rice varieties were at the same level (see table). Carbofuran at 1 kg a.i./ha was effective for gall midge control. The damaged tillers for the treated plots averaged 1.4% at 55 DT. The average number of tillers per hill was higher in the untreated plots because gall midge infestation induced tillering. However, the number of panicles per hill

and grain yield were higher in the treated plots. The percentages of yield losses due to gall midge damage varied. Leaung-Laung showed the greatest yield loss, 32.9%, when 25% of the tillers were damaged, but Niew-San-Pa-Tong had only 7.9% loss at the same level of damage. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Effect of submergence tolerance screening during rapid generation advance on heading duration and productivity

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Heavy rainfall or sudden flooding often causes submergence of tropical rice. The flooding generally occurs during the early growth stages and seriously hampers crop growth.

Previous studies have shown that lines can be screened for submergence tolerance during rapid generation advance (RGA). This report covers the effect of early, total submergence on growth duration and productivity.

Seeds of 7 rice varieties were presoaked and sown in “square” pots (5.1 cm x 5 cm) and vials (3 cm diameter x 4.5 cm height). Only one plant was placed in each container. Ten days after sowing, the seedlings were subjected to 7 days of total submergence. The surviving plants were kept under normal greenhouse

conditions, and the heading dates of each variety were recorded. The mature panicles were harvested and the percentage of seed fertility was recorded.

The same procedures were followed with a control group under normal greenhouse conditions.

Abnormality in flowering and a high degree of spikelet sterility were observed in both the control and submerged plants in the vials. These results were anticipated because of the small amount of soil in the vials and the nutritional

requirements for normal plant growth. The results from the “square” pots are in the table.

The heading duration did not vary greatly between submergence-tolerant varieties. But 3 new semidwarf varieties susceptible to submergence showed 5- to 10-day delays in heading because of early submergence.

Spikelet sterility showed little change in tolerant varieties. In semidwarf varieties, however, change was conspicuous, ranging from 20 to 44

Mean heading duration and spikelet sterility of 7 varieties submerged at seedling stage.

Variety	Survival (%)	Heading duration (days)		Seed sterility (%)	
		Control	Submerged	Control	Submerged
Thavalu 15134	100	68	66	18	28
Thavalu 15235	100	63	65	26	26
FR13A	100	75	74	20	15
KDML 105	50	68	64	30	42
IR38	17	89	94	40	60
IR42	50	73	80	43	80
IR8	38	81	91	13	57
Mean		74	76	27	44
SEM ±			1.5		5.7
Calculated “t”			2.6**		3.1**

** Significant at 0.1 0 level.

percent. Thus, early seedling submergence has little effect on heading duration and productivity of submergence-tolerant varieties. The submergence of the seedlings would not interfere with or delay heading during RGA of tolerant lines. ■

Kneeing ability test of promising deep water rice selections

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Varieties for deepwater rice areas must be able to bend toward the vertical axis so the first three leaves are above the water level. This characteristic known as kneeing ability prevents seed damage by water and aquatic fauna.

Promising deepwater rice cultivars were tested for kneeing ability by a method proposed by Vergara et al (1976). Kneeing was scored on a scale of 1 to 9. Good kneeing ability was shown in 28 of the 58 entries tested (see table). Most entries, which scored 3 and 5, are either local cultivars or pure line selections. Thus, high-volume crossing is needed to create more variability for deepwater rices. ■

Kneeing ability scores of some promising deep-water rice cultures at Patna, India.

Score	Entries (no.)	Entries
3	7	CNL231 B/B, IET6890, KD7-9-20, IET6860, FRG 7, Tilokkachari, and CN603.
5	21	C64-117, BR14, BR46, KLG108-P, KLG173-P, Barobar, KR2-17, KR2-27, CNL108, CM5-13, CN539, CR1009, IET6857, IET6859, NPS7, CN540, CN643, NC486/77, Achra 108/1 and IR7732-RGA-13-A96-1.

Evaluation of rice cultures for submergence tolerance and grain yield under lowland conditions at Tripura

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Hills cover two-thirds of Tripura. The remaining one-third is valley. Most of the lowland valley becomes flooded because rainfall averages 2,000 mm/year. Tripura rice fields remain submerged 1-10 days after a rain, depending upon field drainage. The heavy rainfall and poor drainage prevent high yielding, semidwarf varieties from getting established or giving good yields.

To select a suitable rice variety, 60 new cultures and 13 local varieties were screened for submergence tolerance and grain yield during the rainy seasons of

1978 and 1979. The testing submerged 10- and 20-day-old seedlings in a water tank for 7 days. The water depth ranged from 25 to 30 cm above the seedlings.

Seedling survival increased with age. Most of the varieties showed poor recovery after submergence; however, a few – CR149-5010-228, CR149-3295-4-205, CR210-1005, CR210-1009, CR213-1020-374, and IR2071-176-1-2 – were promising (see table). Some of the cultures gave higher yields than Jagannath, Mahasuri and other local varieties under lowland situations (25-50 cm). Culture CR 149-5010-228 gave the highest average yield during the rainy season.

A seedling emergence percentage count taken on the fourth and seventh days revealed some varieties had faster seedling elongation in water, but reduced survival. They included Jalaplaba, Chenab 64-117, CR149-1744, RAU21-68-1-2, FR13A, Madhukar and Chakia 59. These are all tall traditional varieties and are more suitable for deep water conditions (50-100 cm). ■

Submergence tolerance of some rice cultures and their average grain yield under medium lowland condition, 1978, 1979 rainy season, Tripura, India.^a

Variety	Seedling survival (%)		Av grain yield (t/ha)	Seedling emergence (%) of 10-day-old seedlings	
	10 DS	20 DS		4th day	7th day
CR149-5010-228	68(5)	80(3)	4.4	13	23
CR149-3295-4-205	54(6)	98(2)	3.4	8	11
CR149-1744	68(5)	80(3)	1.5	20	28
CR213-1020-374	40(7)	92(2)	3.5	9	15
RAU21-68-1-2	40(7)	96(2)	2.9	17	34
CR213-1021	27(9)	83(3)	3.2	2	2
CR210-1009	34(8)	69(5)	3.9	–	4
CR210-1005	17(9)	78(4)	3.8	–	4
IR2071-176-1-2	44(7)	89(3)	3.4	2	10
Jagannath ^b	6(9)	81(3)	3.1	–	4
RP1064-14-2-2	38(8)	94(2)	2.7	–	4
Mahasuri ^b	42(7)	87(3)	2.7	12	15
Pijum	21(9)	72(4)	2.4	–	8
Majirsail	19(9)	74(4)	1.7	2	4
BR46	29(9)	68(5)	1.3	6	9
BR14	12(9)	70(5)	1.4	–	–
Chenab 64-117	44(7)	85(3)	1.2	23	30
FR13A	25(9)	76(4)	2.6	10	30
Madhukar	33(8)	75(4)	–	15	25
Chakia 59	51(6)	80(3)	–	13	27
Jalaj	36(8)	54(6)	1.4	15	22
Jaladhi 1	24(9)	44(7)	0.7	8	13
Jaladhi 2	11(9)	78(4)	1.4	9	14
Jalaplaba	37(8)	78(4)	1.8	24	33
C.D. (5%)	–	–	.393	–	–
C.V. %	–	–	15	–	–

^aFigures in the parentheses indicate score value of survival (%). DS = date of seeding. ^bCheck variety.